

and equaled 100% single superphosphate at 3:1 urea ammonium phosphate (see table). Mussorie rock phosphate and phosphate slurry were inefficient.

Single superphosphate, single superphosphate and Mussorie rock phosphate at 1:1 and urea ammonium phosphate were superior for grain P uptake. Full Mussorie rock phosphate and phosphate slurry contributed less P to the grain. □

Effect of P sources on rice yield and P uptake. Bhubaneswar, India.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		P content (%)		P uptake (kg/ha)	
	1980	1981	1980	1981	1980	1981
Single superphosphate 100%	3.0	3.7	0.36	0.37	10.8	13.7
Mussorie rock phosphate 100%	2.6	3.2	0.29	0.32	7.5	10.2
Single superphosphate 75% + Mussorie rock phosphate 25%	2.7	3.6	0.31	0.33	8.4	11.9
Single superphosphate 50% + Mussorie rock phosphate 50%	3.0	3.8	0.35	0.39	10.5	14.8
Urea ammonium phosphate	3.0	3.5	0.36	0.37	10.8	12.9
Diammonium phosphate	2.9	3.5	0.33	0.34	9.6	11.9
Phosphate slurry	2.8	3.0	0.29	0.30	8.1	8.7
Control (60, 0, 30 kg NPK/ha)	2.4	2.9	0.24	0.29	5.7	8.4
CD at 5%	0.4	0.2	0.001	0.002	—	—

Rice-Based Cropping Systems

Irrigated rice-based cropping strategies in coastal Maharashtra

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Most ricefields in coastal Maharashtra remain fallow following one monsoon (Jun-Oct) crop. However, a growing number of medium and small irrigation projects are enabling dry season cropping. Because irrigation water usually is released from mid-Dec to early Jan, we evaluated irrigated crops at 2 planting times, 15 Dec and 5 Jan, in 1983-84 and 1984-85.

Soil was medium black. clayey with 6.3 pH, 0.65% organic C, 28.85 kg available P₂O₅/ha, and 190.0 kg available K₂O/ha. The rice crop (Jaya) transplanted in early Jul and fertilized

Grain yield and net returns of the post-rice dry season crops, by sowing date. Maharashtra, India, 1983-85.

Crop ^a	Grain yield (t/ha)		Net return (\$/ha)	
	15 Dec	5 Jan	15 Dec	5 Jan
Sorghum (120-60-60)	3.27	2.41	290.18	209.87
Wheat (100-50-50)	1.96	2.03	251.67	269.02
Green gram (25-50-0)	0.76	0.42	64.38	26.97
Cowpea (25-50-0)	3.25	2.45	717.29	578.59
Black gram (25-50-0)	0.96	0.53	110.66	3.56
Pigeonpea (25-50-0)	14.8	1.56	243.03	266.22
Groundnut (25-50-0)	3.09	2.99	454.82	426.84
Sunflower (50-30-0)	1.79	1.67	317.30	273.91
Soybean (25-50-0)	0.56	0.37	60.61	92.29
Niger (25-25-0)	0.81	0.34	83.57	50.37
Sesamum (25-25-0)	0.55	0.64	78.34	115.89
Mean			231.87	178.83

^aFigures in parentheses indicate kg NPK/ha.

with 100-50-50 kg NPK/ha yielded 4 t/ha. The post-rice crops were harvested from mid-Mar to late Apr.

In general, early sowing was more profitable than late sowing (see table).

Cowpea sown on 15 Dec had the highest net return (\$717.29/ha). Planting date of wheat, pigeonpea, groundnut, sunflower, and sesamum did not affect net return. □

Announcements

An inside look at the Green Revolution

International agricultural research efforts are providing an extra 50 million tons of grain to the world's poorest countries — enough food to feed almost 500 million people.

according to a new book by Warren Baum.

The author, a former chairman of the Consultative Group on International Agricultural Research (CGIAR) — an international consortium of 34 donors that collectively supports food crop

research in developing countries — says that food crop varieties developed at the CGIAR's 13 international agricultural research centers have dramatically transformed agriculture in developing countries: "Mass starvation, particularly in Asia, has been averted by greater production